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Examining development of the entrepreneurial mind-set in engineering students

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INTRODUCTION

Are students getting more entrepreneurial when following courses with a focus on these competences? Engineering students are increasingly being expected to obtain entrepreneurial competences during their education, and the Technical University of Denmark (DTU) has, like many other universities, rolled out a palette of obligatory and elective courses to meet this need. In this study we build on our previous work to ascertain whether there is a significant difference in the mind-set of students who have taken these courses, compared to those who have not. In a previous study we have investigated whether the course design used in an entrepreneurship course for bachelor of engineering science students resulted in development of an entrepreneurial mind-set or not. The results showed that there is a significant positive development, with respect to different traits identified as central for an entrepreneurial mind-set. The students rated them self in the beginning of the course and then again at the end [1]. A survey developed within the KEEN network (USA) was used and

applied for the students' rating [2]. The mission in KEEN is "to graduate engineers with an entrepreneurial mind-set who can create personal, economic and societal value through meaningful work" [3]. One of the bearing ideas in the KEEN network is to promote development of entrepreneurship because of a learning process through Entrepreneurially Minded Learning (EML). The study in the current paper has the same intentions, to understand more in depth how an entrepreneurial mind-set can be developed within Engineering Education and the same survey is therefore used. Understanding and training the development of an entrepreneurial mind-set has been a hot topic in engineering education literature for some time (e.g. [4]). Often it has focused on students, and thus educations, with a special interest in entrepreneurship. However, as entrepreneurship evolves as an important engineering competence in general and not only for students who actively choose to take part in entrepreneurial activities during their education, we would like to take the next step and broaden the perspective to investigate how engineering students in general understand and develop an entrepreneurial mind-set. Therefore, in this paper we investigate the effects of courses that do not specifically set out to develop entrepreneurial competences. This study is an initial study in order to broaden the perspective on the development of entrepreneurial mind-sets among engineering students and to start to combine different theories about mind-sets and their development in order to deepen the understanding of the processes involved.

1. ENTREPRENEURIAL MIND-SET IN ENGINEERING EDUCATION

In order to investigate the development of a mind-set, it is useful define the concept of mind-set and create a framework to analyse it with respect to its development during education. One definition of a mind-set is that it is our ability to use internal personality traits and mental processes that create a readiness to act and to respond to different situations in a certain manner [5]. Our internal beliefs about ourselves, our abilities and our self-esteem are all involved in a mind-set; "A mental attitude that determines how you will interpret and respond to situations" [6]. In order to create an analytical framework, it is central to consider that our attitudes towards our self, develops in a complex interaction between our environment's responses to our behaviour and then how we, in turn, interpret and react to those responses [7]. The same complex interactions also occur in an education context. In order to develop specific mind-sets through education one of the main question is if education and the learning activities the students are exposed to, can train a certain mind-set. In the work by Dweck two different kinds of mind-sets in education are described to be critical as predictors for success in learning and development of new abilities among students: A fixed and a growth mind-set [8]. A growth mind-set is characterised by the belief that abilities can be developed by training and by the way we are educated. A fixed mind-set is characterized by beliefs that a person has inherited certain personality traits and intellectual abilities that cannot be changed [8]. When it comes to the development of an entrepreneurial mind-set, research often point out the concept of self-efficacy as crucial in order to support students' entrepreneurial abilities [9,10]. The theory of Self-efficacy was developed by Bandura and refers to a person's inner beliefs about his or her own abilities to reach certain goals [11]. If we assume that students have a growth mind-set with respect to education then we can propose that they will be open to training positive personal beliefs and therefore adequate teaching can support development of self-efficacy. This idea can find support by research that shows that the attitudes towards a behaviour is an important predictor of how a mind-set can be expressed and that those attitudes are important to how a person can develop [7]. A

mind-set is internal within a person, but how this person chooses to react in a given situation depends on the cultural and social context and what is allowed and rewarded [9]. Also the attitude towards entrepreneurship and the way of viewing it is central to promoting the development of entrepreneurship as a competence and a method for tackling large and abiding problems [12]. Those are some of the theories forming the background to this study.

2. METHODS TO EXAMINE THE ENTREPRENEURIAL MIND-SET

There are a number of reported methods to examine the entrepreneurial mind-set, one of which is that developed within the KEEN network [2]. KEEN developed a set of 18 questions within four categories, namely: Problem solving, Business acumen, Societal issues and Teamwork, together with a series of questions about the respondent, such as sex, level of current education etc. The questionnaire was used before (pre) and after courses (post). A 5 point Likert scale was used and the results showed that on average the students rated themselves very highly (over 4) even before the courses in question started. Nevertheless, the authors found highly statistically significant increases in the students' entrepreneurial mind-set and concluded that the changes made to their courses and curriculum based on Problem Based Learning were a success. Call et al. [4] also reported an ongoing investigation into the link between an introduction of an entrepreneurial curriculum in an engineering course and the impact on creativity and mind-set. They measured entrepreneurial interest pre and post course using a questionnaire reported by Solesvik [7] which has 26 questions grouped in categories of: Intention to become an entrepreneur, subjective norm, attitude toward behaviour, perceived behavioural control, risk taking and self-efficacy. Furthermore, Call et al. [4] measured creativity using the abbreviated Torrance test for adults (ATTA) also pre and post course. To measure mind-set, they used an online survey also in a pre and post course way (<https://www.mindsetonline.com/testyourmindset/step1.php>). However online tests can pose a challenge for ensuring high completion rates both pre and post course.

3. CONTEXT AND METHODS USED IN THE CURRENT STUDY

In our previous work [1], the entrepreneurial mind-set was investigated in engineering students at the bachelor level who took courses either on entrepreneurship or with a close relationship to it. We saw that there was an increase in the entrepreneurial mind-set at the end of these courses, compared to that at the beginning. However no control courses in which innovation and entrepreneurship were not an explicit part of the curriculum were included. This raises the question of whether the results truly were significant or not and whether the differences we noted earlier were meaningful, or could be due to other factors, such as an overall development in self-efficacy. Here we have therefore investigated the development of the entrepreneurial mind-set in two conventional engineering courses, in which innovation and entrepreneurship were not part of the curriculum and compared the results with those we obtained earlier. All courses (both those we reported on earlier, and in the current study) were taught in 2016-2017 and one of the authors of the current work was involved in teaching all of them. All courses involved group work and groups were formed at the start of the teaching.

The first control course was 23532: "Beer brewing and safe food production". This is a 5 ECTS points practical lab course at masters level taught in a pilot plant brewery over a 3 week period with full-time teaching (8-17 each day). It accepts students at

late bachelor or masters level. The course included two visits to microbreweries, and was assessed by two written reports and an oral exam. The main learning objectives were to learn how to brew beer and to learn how to make the Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points (HACCP) documentation (*i.e.* food safety) needed to be submitted to the authorities to start up a commercial microbrewery. There were ca. 30 students following the course and it had a very applied and commercially relevant focus, but no teaching of entrepreneurial or innovation competences.

The second control course was a chemical engineering course at the masters level on biological purification methods (course 28233) which focuses on the unit operations used in the biotech and pharma industries. This is a 5 ECTS points theoretical course taught in 4 hour blocks over a 13 week period involving lectures, 5 guest lectures from industry, 2 reports, homework and in-class calculation exercises and a 4 hour written exam. There were ca. 50 students actively following the course. The main learning objective was to be able to design (on paper) a process for the purification of a given biological molecule. This course was very much orientated towards giving engineering students skills needed for process design and there was no teaching of entrepreneurial or innovation competences.

A third course (23552 “Innovation in future foods”) was included where learning objectives on innovation and entrepreneurship were the primary focus. It was a 5 ECTS points practical course which accepts bachelor and master students in which the main learning objective is for the students to be able to invent and make a new innovative sustainable food prototype and develop the business case for its commercialisation. Although only 5 ECTS points, this involves substantial extra-curricular effort and ran nominally over a 13 weeks period with teaching in 4 hour blocks each week. It involved lectures, guest lectures, practical and field work and ended with a ‘venture-cup’ type competition. There were 8 students and development of innovation and entrepreneurial skills is a core learning outcome.

3.1 DATA COLLECTION

The KEEN entrepreneurial mindset questionnaire was modified by eliminating the student specific questions (sex, age etc), leaving only the key questions needed to assess the entrepreneurial mindset (Table 1). This was done in order to reduce the overall number of questions to ensure a high completion rate of honest answers. A hardcopy of the survey was then given to each student on the first day (pre) of the relevant course and again on the last day of formal teaching on the course (post), but before the exam. It was filled out by the students in the class room on the day it was handed out and collected immediately to ensure a high participation rate. The same procedure was followed on the last day of the course, in which close to 100% of the students following a course were present. The surveys were filled out anonymously, but the students were asked to indicate the education they were taking. The students were given strict instructions to fill out the survey as honestly as possible, with answers corresponding only to their current mind-set.

4. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS AND RESULTS OF THE SURVEY

The result of the survey and a statistical analysis are presented for courses 28233, 23532 and 23552. The pre-test is referred to as pre28233, pre23532 or pre23552 and the post-test is referred to as post28233, post23532 or post23552. Data for all courses were collected in 2017. This gives 6 batches of answers named as described above.

Data consists of 32 observations from pre28233, 33 observations from post28233, 24 observations from pre23532, 26 observations from post23532, 8 observations from pre23552, and 8 observations from post23552. For all questions (Table 1) the answers were given on a 5 point Likert scale: 1 indicates "Strongly disagree"; 3 "neutral" and 5 "Strongly agree".

Table 1. Entrepreneurial mindset questionnaire used in the current study¹.

Nr.	Mindset in question	Mindset type ²
1	I am able to recognize problems that exist in the world around me.	P
2	I am good at devising multiple solutions when solving problems	P
3	I continue trying even after I have failed.	P
4	I ask relevant questions to clarify situations and gain new knowledge.	P
5	I am able to independently gain new information from various sources.	P
6	I accept responsibility for my personal actions	P
7	I accept responsibility for the work I produce, including mistakes	P
8	I think outside the box and am creative.	P
9	I understand and identify with the feelings, experiences, and motives of others	T
10	I am aware of my personal strengths and weaknesses	T
11	I can identify strengths and weaknesses in others	T
12	I am able to determine whether I should lead or follow in different situations	T
13	I can develop and maintain working relationships with peers	T
14	I can develop and maintain working relationships with supervisors or superiors	T
15	I am capable of resolving conflict	T
16	I am able to verbally organize and communicate ideas appropriate to the situation.	B
17	I am able to organize and communicate ideas in writing appropriate to the situation	B
18	I understand basic principles of business.	B
19	I understand how marketing is used effectively within an organization.	B
20	I understand the concepts of finance in a business setting.	B
21	I assess opportunity and recognize unmet needs.	B
22	I assess and undertake reasonable risks.	B
23	I can develop my own vision.	B
24	I think and behave ethically	S
25	I am aware of how global issues influence society	S
26	I serve the needs of others.	S
27	I try to make environmentally sensitive decisions.	S
28	I aim to make a positive impact on society.	S

¹ From [10]. ² P= problem solving & critical thinking; T=teamwork; B=business acumen; S=societal issues

The data were collected on paper to ensure that the answers were given in an anonymous way and it is thus not possible to have paired observations (i.e. which pre and post questionnaires come from the same student). Having had that information would have allowed a more powerful statistical analysis and it is worthwhile to consider whether it can be possible to get that information in future studies. As a part of filling out the questionnaire the students are asked to state their study direction. Unfortunately, this was not done by all the students, which would have been useful to see if there are differences between different educations.

4.1 Statistical analysis

The mean scores for each mind-set category (Table 2) show a tendency that after having attended one of the courses the scores are higher than before attending. However, for group S in course 23552 there is a small decrease. All the changes are

insignificant ($p > 0.05$) except for group P in course 23532. This is unexpected since entrepreneurial competences are not taught there, however, due to the possibility of mass significance problems this could be only by chance. It can also be seen that the students rate themselves highly before the course start (well over 3.5 in most cases) and even higher Pre scores (all over 4) were reported by Carpenter et al [10]. Interestingly the B categories (business acumen) are statistically significantly lower compared to the other mind-set categories, whether Pre or Post scores. However, the scores for P, T and S appear similar to each other (although statistically different) when compared before the course and is also seen when compared after the course.

Table 2. Average values for answers in the mindset categories of P, T, B and S

Course	Pre	Post	Significant difference (P < 0.05)	Mindset category ^{1,2}
28233	3.98	4.07	No	P
23532	4.07	4.35	No	P
23552	3.92	4.30	No	P
28233	3.81	3.81	No	T
23532	3.74	3.95	No	T
23552	4.04	4.18	No	T
28233	3.43	3.60	No	B
23532	3.41	3.63	No	B
23552	3.48	3.85	No	B
28233	3.85	3.85	No	S
23532	4.12	4.22	No	S
23552	3.95	3.88	No	S
28233	3.77	3.84	Yes	Overall mean
23532	3.84	4.04	No	Overall mean
23552	3.85	4.07	No	Overall mean

1. P= Problem solving and critical thinking; T= Teamwork; B= business acumen; S=societal issues
2. Overall mean represents the mean score for all questions for the course under evaluation.

When the results (*i.e* no significant change pre versus post) found in Table 2 for control courses are compared to what we reported for the course “High-Tech Entrepreneurship” in (2016, 2017) [1] we see some important differences. Most importantly, for all four mind-set groups, a significant increase was found in the scores after taking that course compared to before (p -values < 0.005) [1]. When compared to the control results in Table 2, we can thus conclude that the course on high-tech entrepreneurship did indeed lead to a significant increase in the entrepreneurial mind-set. The strongest effect seen by Rootzén et al [1] was in the mind-set group S where it was estimated to be 2.1. For the rest of the groups it was estimated to be 0.61 (P), 0.69 (T) and 0.66 (B). S was estimated to be much lower before the course and reached the same level as P, T, and B by the end of the course [1]. This pattern is not seen in the new data for the control courses.

5. DISCUSSION AND FUTURE WORK

Overall the average ‘Pre’ scores are high (over 3.4) in the study we conducted here, as well as in our previous study [1], and also in the KEEN study [2]. Given that 3 represents neutral agreement with the statement questioned (Table1) and 4 represents ‘agree’, the observations suggests that on average, at best only 3 (or even 2) points on the scale are being used. The results suggest that the 5 point Likert scale used here should be modified in future work to allow more differentiation between mind-set at the start of a course and that at the end. This would allow more detailed

analysis of the student self-rating in a survey. However the results raise other questions about the mechanisms in play when the students answer the questionnaire, which may skew the results. For example whether the students are able to judge themselves on entrepreneurial competences if they do not already have knowledge about what is being asked for? Are the students' expectations about how they are supposed to be as engineering students a hinder for honest answers to surveys of this kind? Do the students in the previous study [1] have a greater interest in entrepreneurship and can judge their own abilities better?

The results suggest that on average the students believe that they do not have low entrepreneurial traits or self-efficacy before the courses start – even for control courses. However, it is well documented that only a low percent of the population will end as entrepreneurs. It could be speculated that the massive focus on innovation and entrepreneurship education over the last 10 years, even at the junior-high and high-school level has led to a high baseline competence in these areas. In support of this, the 2018 Global Entrepreneurship rankings show that Denmark is ranked 6th in the world (USA being number 1; Switzerland number 2). This raises the question of how education should be conducted to raise the students from an already apparently high entrepreneurial mind-set level to an even higher one that will result in improved innovation and entrepreneurship in society. Pedagogical approaches are probably needed, where there is better alignment between education and real-life entrepreneurship, and where a growth mind-set towards education is ensured [8] and students self-efficacy is consciously trained [11]. To assess the effect of these, more complex and mixed approaches towards education and teaching, studies with a triangulation approach may be required in order to capture the nature of development of an entrepreneurial mind-set among the students. A longitudinal study where students' development of entrepreneurial mind-set and competences are followed during a longer time would be probably be useful. These considerations will form the basis for a larger study about the development of entrepreneurial competences and mind-sets among engineering students in cooperation between DTU, in Copenhagen, and EPFL, Lausanne, within EuroTech University Alliance.

7. SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We have employed a survey used by the KEEN network to investigate the development of the entrepreneurial mind-set in control courses where innovation and entrepreneurship were not specifically taught and compared these to courses where innovation and entrepreneurship were a central part of the learning objectives. Surprisingly, the results showed that there was a weak trend (not statistically significantly) showing a positive development in the entrepreneurial mind-set in the control courses. Furthermore, the students score themselves very high on the questions posed, both before and after a course. The results raise questions about the adequacy of the surveys used as the only tool for quantifying development of the entrepreneurial mind-set in engineering students. It also indicates that more parameters must be included in a study. Those could for example be to investigate if the faculty teaching courses apply a growth mind-set as their teaching strategy. Such a strategy in itself can be a reason for students to experience that they develop on the traits that define an entrepreneurial mind-set in the KEEN survey. To shed further light on this, DTU and EPFL have initiated an inter-university collaboration and the results will be presented in a future reports.

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